

WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND THE EXTENT OF EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY AMONG THE COMMISSION ON AUDIT REGIONAL OFFICE NO. XII PERSONNEL UNDER WORK-FROM-HOME ARRANGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The post-pandemic era has witnessed a global adoption of Work-from-Home (WFH) arrangements that have profoundly transformed traditional work paradigms, especially in the public sector. This study aims to investigate the perceived levels of work-life balance and the extent of employee productivity among personnel of the Commission on Audit (COA) Regional Office No. XII under a WFH arrangement. The work-life balance focuses on five key indicators, which are stress level, time management, personal satisfaction, flexibility, and technology and resources, while productivity is assessed in terms of output, task completion rate, efficiency, self-reported productivity, and additional perspectives on output. This study employed surveys and in-depth interviews to assess the relationship between work-life balance and productivity under the WFH arrangements. The findings reveal that the WFH arrangement leads to a high level of work-life balance. However, while they agree, respondents are not totally convinced that WFH leads to increased productivity. Moreover, the results confirm that work-life balance significantly influences the employees' productivity under the WFH arrangements. Respondents consider the high volume of workload, boundaries between professional and personal duties, and the struggle to disengage as the main challenges under the new arrangement. Findings from this study offer valuable insights for public sector organizations, especially in the Philippines.

Keywords: *Work-from-home arrangement, work-life balance, productivity, public sector*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought significant transformations to organizations around the world. Government lockdowns and limited mobility have then challenged and threatened the survival and operations of organizations and their management. To avoid disruptions, organizations have been forced to become resilient by introducing innovations and practices. Innovative practices were introduced not only in the field of healthcare and business but also in the public sector.

One of these innovations was the introduction of the Work-from-Home (WFH) arrangement. Under the arrangement, employees were allowed to perform their tasks and jobs from their remote homes. The WFH arrangements have different faces and vary among organizations. Many agencies have experienced the success of telecommuting and non-traditional work hours without compromising productivity, making the offering of flexible work arrangements more common (Fazal et al, 2022). With the lifting of social distancing orders and the reopening of businesses and government agencies, flexible work arrangements, including remote work, have become a standard practice. This setup continued in many organizations around the world even after the pandemic.

In the Philippines, the WFH arrangement in the public sector was introduced by the Civil Service Commission (CSC) to ensure the protection of health, safety, and welfare not just for their central and regional personnel but also for other government agencies that will drive employee well-being and performance with uninterrupted public service during official work hours. The Commission on Audit Regional Office XII (COA ROXII) in Koronadal City is one of the organizations that adopted and continues to implement the WFH arrangement after the pandemic.

The WFH arrangement has been implemented for a considerable time already. However, its effect is a subject of ongoing debate. The literature claimed that WFH arrangements improved work-life balance through reduced commuting time and increased flexibility, increased productivity due to reduced distractions and increased autonomy, and reduced environmental impact (Bloom et al, 2015). However, potential challenges include blurred boundaries between work and personal life (Bulger et al, 2021), leading to increased stress and burnout (Irfan et al, 2021); social isolation and loneliness (Miller, 2020); challenges for certain professions (Gaduena et al, 2022); and potential inequities in access to technology and opportunities (Matli et al, 2023). Moreover, not all organizations can implement WFH arrangements successfully. The success of WFH implementation is highly determined by the presence and availability of certain organizational elements. These elements are recognition of individual employees' differences, well-established organizational culture and policies, dependable technological ecosystem, and supportive government policies.

While the literature has confirmed the positive effect of work-life balance on employees' productivity (Anakpo et al, 2023), there is a need to examine their relationship under the WFH arrangement. A significant gap exists in understanding the nuanced interplay among specific WHF arrangements in the public sector, employees' work-life balance, and productivity within the context of COA ROXII.

In response to this need and to identify the most responsive alternative work arrangement, this study aimed to determine the extent of work-life balance and the level of employees' productivity under the WFH arrangements. It investigates the interplay between employees' work-life balance and productivity. Moreover, the opportunities and challenges experienced by the employees under such arrangements were also examined.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of work-life balance of the COA Region XII employees under the Work-from-Home Arrangement in terms of stress level, time management, personal satisfaction, flexibility, technology, and resources?
2. What is the extent of employees' productivity under the Work-from-Home Arrangement in terms of output, task completion rate, efficiency, self-reported productivity, additional perspectives on output?
3. Is there a relationship between work-life balance under WFH and employees' productivity under WFH?

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive-correlational research design shown in Figure 2 was appropriate for studying the effect of work-from-home (WFH) arrangements on work-life balance for personnel at the Commission on Audit (COA) Regional Office No. XII. This design was selected because it allows for the exploration of the relationships between WFH arrangements and various aspects of employee work-life balance, such as productivity, stress levels, time management, and personal satisfaction (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). The descriptive aspect of the study focused on gathering data that described the current situation of COA employees working from home. At the same time, the correlational part analyzed how these variables related to one another, establishing whether there were significant associations between the WFH setup and changes in work-life balance.

This design aligned to assess the effectiveness of WFH policies in promoting a balance between work responsibilities and personal life without manipulating any variables, thus reflecting real-life circumstances (Cohen et al, 2018). The descriptive approach enabled the study to measure the perceptions of employees regarding the benefits and challenges of working from home. At the same time, the correlational method provided insights into whether these perceptions were linked to measurable outcomes, such as increased productivity or reduced stress (Bryman, 2012).

The quantitative approach was applied by using a structured survey instrument based on Likert scale questions. This instrument measured various dimensions of work-life balance, including stress levels, time management, personal satisfaction, flexibility, and technology and resources. Such instruments had been adapted and validated in previous Research, such as the studies of Golden et al. (2015) and Hammer et al. (2010), which explored the intersections of work-life balance and productivity in remote work contexts. By using standardized questionnaires, the Research ensured consistency and reliability in measuring the perceptions of COA employees, thereby enhancing the generalizability of the findings (Saunders et al., 2016).

For data collection, the survey was electronically distributed to the personnel of COA Regional Office No. XII, given their familiarity with remote work and technology. The survey collected data from a representative sample of employees, providing insights into how the WFH arrangement affected them across different job functions and seniority levels. The quantitative data were analyzed using statistical software, applying descriptive statistics and correlation analyses to identify patterns and relationships among the variables of interest (Field, 2013).

Therefore, a descriptive-correlational design was most suitable for this Research as it allowed for the exploration of multiple dimensions of work-life balance in remote work, providing data-driven insights into the impact of WFH arrangements on COA employees.

The purposive sampling approach gathered data from COA Regional Office No. XII personnel who had been involved in a WFH arrangement. The target participants for this study included personnel across different job levels—administrative staff, auditors, supervisors, and managerial positions—who had been engaged in a WFH setup for a significant period, ideally for at least six months. The period ensured they had sufficient experience to provide meaningful insights into how the WFH arrangement had impacted their productivity and work-life balance.

Purposive sampling, as described by Etikan et al. (2016), allowed researchers to strategically select participants who could provide the most relevant and detailed information. In this study, not all COA employees had had experience with WFH arrangements, so the selection process focused on those whose work tasks were adaptable to remote work, which ensured that the participants could provide valuable insights into the WFH experience.

As Palinkas et al. (2015) pointed out, purposive sampling was well-suited for exploratory Research where the objective was to gain a detailed understanding of a specific group. In this Research, it was vital to include the perspectives of individuals who had directly managed the shift to remote work. These individuals could offer valuable insights into both productivity results and the challenges of balancing work and personal responsibilities during remote work arrangements.

Purposive sampling was used to select respondents who were best suited to provide insights into the Research questions. This method allows for the inclusion of individuals from different job roles, ensuring that the findings capture the diverse experiences within COA Regional Office No. XII.

Therefore, purposive sampling was an appropriate method for this study, as it directly addressed the specific focus on WFH experiences. This targeted approach facilitated the collection of precise and relevant data, ultimately contributing to a deeper understanding of the impact of WFH arrangements on employee productivity and work-life balance within the context of COA.

A total of 50 participants was selected using purposive sampling, a non-random sampling technique where individuals are chosen based on specific criteria relevant to the Research objectives. As Etikan et al. (2016) explained, purposive sampling enabled the selection of participants with specific knowledge, skills, or experiences pertinent to the Research topic. In this study, respondents must have engaged in WFH arrangements for at least six months to ensure they had meaningful and comprehensive experiences to share.

The target respondents comprised personnel from diverse departments and job levels within COA Regional Office No. XII, ranging from administrative staff to auditors and managerial staff. These individuals must have experienced the transition from a traditional office setting to a WFH setup, as they were uniquely qualified to comment on the impact of this arrangement on both their productivity (e.g., task completion, output, efficiency) and their perceived work-life balance (e.g., stress levels, time management, personal satisfaction). This selection process aligned with the recommendations of Palinkas et al. (2015), who emphasized that purposive sampling was practical when targeting specific individuals with the necessary expertise and experience to address the Research questions.

To ensure the relevance and representativeness of the Research findings, it was essential to define clear inclusion and exclusion criteria for a study on the optimal effect of WFH arrangements on work-life balance for COA Regional Office No. XII personnel. Clear inclusion and exclusion criteria not only streamlined participant selection but also enhanced the study's reliability by focusing on the relevant sample population (Sim & Wright, 2000).

To be eligible for this study, participants must meet several specific criteria. Current employment at COA Regional Office No. XII was a requirement so that participants were familiar with both the organization's WFH policies and their job tasks in a remote work setting. Moreover, employees must have been part of the WFH arrangement for at least six months. According to Faulds et al. (2021), this time frame allowed workers sufficient experience with the system to offer valuable insights into how the WFH arrangement had impacted their work-life balance and productivity.

Additionally, participants must be full-time employees, defined as those working a minimum of 35-40 hours per week, as full-time employees had more consistent schedules and responsibilities, which were critical for studying work-life balance (Kossek & Lautsch, 2018), and the work-from-home experience being evaluated was substantial. Employees must also have access to the necessary technology (e.g., computers, reliable internet, collaboration software), as technology was a critical factor in the success of remote work arrangements (Golden & Veiga, 2005).

The Research specifically examined COA Regional Office No. XII, which adopted a WFH arrangement in response to the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic and subsequent flexible work policies. This regional office was chosen due to its accessibility, the availability of personnel who met the study's inclusion criteria, and its adoption of WFH practices. The geographical scope was essential as it provided a focused context to examine the specific impact of WFH arrangements within a government audit institution.

By gathering data from respondents within this specific locale, the study was able to assess how the WFH arrangement had affected the work and life balance of COA personnel within the region. This setting also allowed for an in-depth examination of local challenges, such as internet connectivity and technology access, which may uniquely influence the experience of WFH in this region.

To effectively assess the optimum effect of the work-from-home (WFH) arrangement on the work-life balance of personnel in Commission on Audit Regional Office No. XII, the Research instrumentation was based on adapted and developed questionnaires from existing validated tools such as those used by Baker et al. (2007), Stroom (2023), and Ismawati et al. (2023). The primary data collection instrument was a structured questionnaire to quantitatively measure WFH's impact on work-life balance and employee productivity.

The survey included three key sections. The first section gathered demographic data, including age, gender, job role, years of service, and the nature of their WFH arrangement (e.g., full-time, hybrid). This section was critical for contextualizing the responses and identifying patterns across employee demographics.

The second section assessed work-life balance, with subcategories addressing stress levels, time management, and personal satisfaction. Adapted from existing work-life balance scales, this section included statements such as 'I feel less stressed when working from home' and 'I manage my time between work and family better while in a WFH setup.' Responses are measured using a 5-point Likert scale.

The third section focused on employee productivity. Participants responded to statements using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree." Sample statements might include: "I complete more tasks while working from home compared to the office" or "I find it easier to meet deadlines in a WFH setup." This

section assessed various productivity metrics such as output, task completion rate, and work efficiency.

An online survey questionnaire was utilized in gathering the responses of the respondents. Using a Google form, the researcher saved track of the progress of the responses among the COA personnel. Online surveys were carried out using mobile phones, PCs, tablets, and other gadgets with internet connectivity. The questionnaire included a letter of information of consent disclosing the purpose of the study and other details. Some COA personnel prefer the hard copy of the survey questionnaires. Hence, it was also provided for their perusal.

The link to the online survey questionnaire in Google Forms was sent to the selected COA personnel via Facebook Messenger or personal email. For ethical considerations, the researcher strictly adhered to all necessary procedures in acquiring the responses of COA personnel. The scale below was used with a corresponding description to evaluate the level of effectivity of the WFH arrangement perceived by the COA Region XII personnel:

Table 1. Effectivity Scale Interpretation

Likert Scale/ Mean score		Effectiveness
Strongly Agree	4.5 – 5.0	Effective
Agree	3.5 – 4.4	Effective
Neither Agree or Disagree	2.5 – 3.4	Approaching Effectivity
Disagree	1.5 – 2.4	Developing Effectivity
Strongly Disagree	1.0 – 1.4	Developing Effectivity

Note. This table outlines the interpretation of mean scores based on a 5-point Likert scale to determine effectiveness.

Table 1 outlines a system for understanding Likert scale mean scores in terms of effectiveness in this study. It categorized mean scores into different levels of effectiveness based on their range and corresponding Likert scale descriptors. Mean score ranging from 4.5 to 5.0, associated with "Strongly Agree," is considered "Effective". Similarly, a mean score of 3.5 to 4.4, linked to "Agree," was also interpreted as "Effective". Moving down the scale, a mean score of 2.5 to 3.4, representing "Neither Agree or Disagree," indicated "Approaching Effectivity". Mean scores between 1.5 and 2.4, corresponding to "Disagree," were classified as "Developing Effectivity". The lowest range, 1.0 to 1.4, associated with "Strongly Disagree," was also interpreted as "Developing Effectivity". It measured the respondents' level of work-life balance and the extent of their employee productivity, with data gathered from the survey.

For problems one and two, respondents' responses were tallied and subjected to statistical treatment using the Excel Average Formula through the Statistical Package for Social Sciences v. 23 (SPSS) for Windows. This statistical measure will likely be used to interpret the Likert scale responses for work-life balance and productivity levels. The data

was computed using the weighted mean rating method for each item in the questionnaire. To properly interpret the results, the descriptions were used in conjunction with the weighted mean, which offered a quantitative representation of the respondents' responses on the five-point scale. This strategy enabled a thorough understanding of the effectiveness of the Work-from-Home arrangement for the COA ROXII personnel.

For Problem 3, Inferential Statistics using Spearman Rank Correlation was used. This non-parametric test was utilized to measure the strength and direction of the monotonic relationship between the level of work-life balance and the extent of employee productivity under the Work-from-Home Arrangement.

The researcher conducted the study following the highest ethical standards, study and adhering to consistent measurements and evaluations, especially in the management of people and data, including but not restricted to respondents involved possessing the ability to participate freely without fear of consequences or fines. Therefore, the study's purpose and benefits were presented to the respondents. If, at any point, participants felt uncomfortable answering any question, they could withdraw from the survey.

The private and personal data of the responders was maintained. Private and given the highest level of discretion, the names of respondents never appeared, and only the researcher was aware of it concerning the respondents' particular responses. In order to maintain confidentiality, the researcher gave the answers a numerical code that only the researcher could obtain the key that showed which number went with each reply. Following the extraction of data from the completed surveys, they were handled according to the regular procedure of the ethics and review committee. Only the selected respondents were allowed to participate in the study. Throughout the research process, data and samples were regularly collected and stored. To maintain public trust, data protection measures were developed and communicated to Research participants. Results were securely stored until publication, as it was crucial to protect the sources of information. Additionally, measures were implemented to physically safeguard and secure the data and computers storing sensitive information.

Additionally, the researcher ensured that respondents were treated with respect and fairness, regardless of gender, ethnicity, culture, or faith. This Research was conducted objectively and without bias and granted exemption from review by the Mindanao State University-General Santos Institutional Ethics Review Committee for implementation.

Lastly, confidentiality agreements were implemented. Respondents were appropriately asked to participate by obtaining informed consent, a fundamental mechanism to ensure that individuals were treated with respect and fairness by providing thoughtful support for a voluntary act. Similarly, the Research electronic questionnaire shall only be administered with permission from the authorized command channels.

RESULTS

Table 2. Level of WFH Arrangement Affect Employees Perceived Work-Life Balance

Indicator	WM	Description
Stress level		
1. I feel less stressed when working from home compared to working in the office.	4.06	Agree
2. The work-from-home arrangement has helped me manage work-related stress better.	4.52	Strongly Agree
3. I find it easier to maintain emotional balance while working from home.	4.46	Agree
4. I feel more relaxed during my work hours when working from home.	4.60	Strongly Agree
5. I experience fewer stress-induced physical symptoms (e.g., headaches, fatigue) when working from home.	4.52	Strongly Agree
Mean	4.43	Agree
Time Management		
1. I am able to manage my time more effectively when working from home.	4.34	Agree
2. I have improved my ability to balance work and personal responsibilities while working from home.	4.50	Strongly Agree
3. Working from home allows me to allocate more time to my personal life.	4.58	Strongly Agree
4. I can complete work tasks more efficiently when working from home, leaving more time for personal activities.	4.26	Agree
5. I am able to set clear boundaries between work time and personal time when working from home.	4.26	Agree
Mean	4.39	Agree
Personal Satisfaction		
1. I am more satisfied with my work-life balance when working from home.	4.58	Strongly Agree
2. I feel more fulfilled with my personal life because of the flexibility of working from home.	4.62	Strongly Agree
3. Working from home allows me to engage in personal hobbies or interests more often.	4.40	Agree
4. I feel more in control of my life when working from home.	4.36	Agree

5. I am satisfied with the balance between my work and personal responsibilities while working from home.	4.52	Strongly Agree
Mean	4.50	Strongly Agree
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Flexibility		
1. The flexibility of the WFH arrangement allows me to manage my work and personal responsibilities more effectively.	4.56	Strongly Agree
2. I feel that WFH flexibility helps me maintain a healthier balance between my professional and personal life.	4.56	Strongly Agree
3. The ability to set my work hours in a WFH setup improves my work-life balance.	4.52	Strongly Agree
4. The flexibility of working from home gives me more control over my daily schedule, enhancing my overall work-life balance.	4.48	Agree
5. I am able to adjust my working hours to accommodate personal needs without negatively affecting my work performance.	4.50	Strongly Agree
Mean	4.52	Strongly Agree
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Technology and Resources		
1. I have access to the necessary technology and tools that help me balance work tasks and personal responsibilities while working from home.	4.36	Agree
2. The availability of reliable technology resources makes it easier for me to maintain a healthy work-life balance in the WFH setup.	4.40	Agree
3. My work-from-home experience is enhanced by the efficiency of the technology I use, which helps me manage both work and life effectively.	4.28	Agree
4. I feel that my work productivity and personal satisfaction have improved due to the availability of technology and resources at home.	4.40	Agree
5. The technological support I receive in the WFH arrangement allows me to focus on my tasks without impacting my time.	4.30	Agree
Mean	4.35	Agree
Over-all Mean	4.44	Agree

Note. WM = Weighted Mean. The descriptive equivalents are: 1.00-1.75 = Strongly Disagree, 1.76-2.50 = Disagree, 2.51-3.25 = Neutral, 3.26-4.00 = Agree, and 4.01-5.00 = Strongly Agree. The overall mean of 4.44 indicates a high level of work-life balance under the Work-from-home arrangement. Personal satisfaction and flexibility had the highest mean levels, both described as "very high," while stress level, time management, and technology and resources were rated as "high."

Table 3. Extent of Work-From-Home Arrangement Influence Employee Productivity

Indicator	WM	Description
Output		
1. I have completed more tasks since I started working from home.	4.06	Agree
2. The number of projects I complete in a month has increased while working from home.	3.98	Agree
3. I find it easier to meet my task completion goals while working from home.	4.12	Agree
4. I am more productive with my time management when working from home.	4.20	Agree
5. I can complete tasks more quickly when working from home compared to the office.	4.02	Agree
Mean	4.08	Agree
Task Completion Rate		
1. I complete my tasks on time more frequently when working from home.	4.04	Agree
2. I have a higher task completion rate since switching to a work-from-home arrangement.	4.02	Agree
3. I feel confident in my ability to meet deadlines while working from home.	4.32	Agree
4. I experience less stress about meeting deadlines when working from home.	4.32	Agree
5. I feel that my time management skills have improved while working from home.	4.24	Agree
Mean	4.19	Agree
Efficiency of Task Completion		
1. I am able to complete tasks with greater efficiency while working from home.	4.14	Agree
2. I can utilize technology effectively to enhance my output while working from home.	4.30	Agree
3. I take fewer resources (time, tools) to complete tasks when working from home.	4.16	Agree
4. I find that the work-from-home arrangement helps me streamline my tasks.	4.30	Agree
5. I have reduced the time taken to complete tasks since working from home.	4.20	Agree

	Mean	
	4.22	Agree
Additional Perspectives on Output		
1. I feel that working from home has helped me develop new skills that enhance my output.	4.22	Agree
2. I believe that my contributions to the team have increased since I began working from home.	4.18	Agree
3. I communicate my progress on tasks more effectively while working from home.	4.04	Agree
4. I often seek feedback on my tasks from colleagues to improve my output while at home.	4.00	Agree
5. I have access to necessary tools and resources at home, enabling me to complete tasks efficiently.	4.28	Agree
	Mean	4.14
Self-reported productivity		
1. I believe that my productivity has significantly improved during the work-from-home arrangement.	4.22	Agree
2. I have set clear productivity goals for myself while working from home.	4.28	Agree
3. I feel accountable for my productivity when working from home.	4.48	Agree
4. I track my productivity daily when working from home.	4.24	Agree
5. I regularly reflect on my work output to make improvements while working from home.	4.22	Agree
	Mean	4.29
Over-all Mean	4.18	Agree

Note. WM = Weighted Mean. The descriptive equivalents are: 1.00-1.75 = Strongly Disagree, 1.76-2.50 = Disagree, 2.51-3.25 = Neutral, 3.26-4.00 = Agree, and 4.01-5.00 = Strongly Agree.

The overall computed mean of 4.18, described as "agree," indicates that the respondents perceive a high extent of influence of the work-from-home arrangement on their employee productivity. This implies a positive and substantial impact across all dimensions examined, with consistent perceptions of improved performance, efficiency, and goal attainment.

Table 4. Relationship Between Level of Work-Life Balance and the Extent of Productivity Under the Work-from-Home Arrangement of COA Region XII Employees Using Spearman's rho

Variables Correlated	r	r ²	p-value	Extent of Relationship	Remark
Level of Work-Life Balance and the Extent of Productivity Under the Work-from-Home Arrangement of COA ROXII Employees	.841	.707	.000	High	Significant

DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the overall computed mean of **4.44** indicates that the respondents have a high level of work-life balance under the Work-from-Home arrangement. The dimensions with the highest levels were personal satisfaction and flexibility, both described as very high, while stress level, time management, and technology and resources were rated as high. These results reinforce the growing body of literature that supports the effectiveness of remote work in enhancing employees' quality of life and reducing the strain from traditional office-based work settings.

Over-all results of the level of work-life balance confirmed establishing clear boundaries about when the workday starts and ends helps to prevent burnout and maintain separation between the two" align with the concept of hygiene factors that mitigate dissatisfaction. The positive spillover from work to family, which is facilitated by good work-life balance, also contributes to overall well-being and indirectly to job satisfaction (Lomakin, 2022) and that flexible work acts as a hygiene factor, contributing to retention by reducing dissatisfaction (Almeida & Santos, 2024).

Table 3 shows that the computed overall mean is **4.18**, described as agreeing. This implies that the respondents have a high extent of work-from-home arrangements influencing employee productivity. The results indicate that the Work-from-Home Arrangement has a positive and substantial impact on employee productivity across all examined dimensions. The mean values across the subscales confirm a consistent perception of improved performance, efficiency, and goal attainment. These results are reinforced by related empirical studies, which demonstrate that remote work, when supported with appropriate tools, autonomy, and feedback mechanisms, contributes significantly to employee productivity.

These studies underscore that a holistic approach, addressing both hygiene factors to prevent dissatisfaction and actively cultivating motivator factors to foster genuine engagement, is essential for organizations aiming to maximize employee

productivity according to Herzberg's theoretical underpinnings (Freedman, 2024) and that both sets of factors are important, albeit in different ways, for overall productivity (McLeod, 2023).

Table 4 shows that there is a high positive significant correlation between the level of work-life balance and the extent of productivity under the Work from Home Arrangement of the COA Region XII employees, $r(50) = .841, p = .000 < .05$, explaining 70.7% of the variations in the extent of employees' productivity under the Work from Home Arrangement. The remaining 29.3% of the variance may be influenced by other factors such as personal motivation, type of work, leadership, access to tools, or home environment. These results imply that the level of work-life balance significantly influences the extent of productivity under the Work-from-Home Arrangement of the COA Region XII employees. These findings also suggest that as the level of work-life balance increases, so does their extent of productivity under the Work from Home Arrangement. Choudhury et al. (2021) confirmed that remote work enhances performance by providing flexibility, which in turn improves job satisfaction and output.

The findings in this study support the conclusion that work-life balance is a strong predictor of productivity in WFH settings. Employees who can manage their professional and personal responsibilities effectively are more likely to deliver efficient and quality outcomes.

The results also indicate that the WFH arrangement has been largely successful in enhancing both work-life balance and productivity among COA Region XII employees. This success reflects the employees' adaptability, commitment, and the region's efforts to support remote work. The finding that employees feel more relaxed and experience less stress under WFH could be particularly relevant in COA Region XII. If employees in this region typically face longer commutes or experience specific workplace pressures, the WFH arrangement might offer a significant respite, contributing to the high level of work-life balance observed. The improvement in time management and the ability to balance work and personal responsibilities can be highly beneficial in a regional context. This could imply that employees in COA Region XII may have significant family responsibilities or engage in local community activities that require flexible time management. The strong agreement on feeling more fulfilled and having greater control over their lives suggests that the WFH arrangement aligns well with the employees' values and lifestyle in COA Region XII. This might indicate a cultural emphasis on family and personal well-being in the region. The agreement that technology and resources facilitate work-life balance highlights the importance of infrastructure in COA Region XII. If there are challenges related to internet connectivity or access to resources, the fact that employees still find technology helpful suggests that efforts have been made to address these issues.

The reported increase in productivity, including better time management and task completion, suggests that the WFH arrangement enables employees in COA Region XII to work efficiently. This could be important for the region's development and the effectiveness of government services. The confidence in meeting deadlines and the

higher task completion rate under WFH indicate that employees in COA Region XII are responsible and committed to their work, even in a remote setting. The efficient use of technology and streamlined tasks reflects the adaptability of employees in COA Region XII to new work methods. This is crucial for maintaining productivity and service delivery in the region. Access to tools and skill development opportunities suggests that employees in Region XII are motivated to improve their performance and contribute to the organization's goals. The sense of accountability and goal-setting demonstrates the self-discipline and work ethic of employees in COA Region XII.

The study strongly indicates that WFH positively influences Herzberg's "motivators". Increased output, improved task completion rates, and efficient task completion suggest employees experience a greater sense of achievement under WFH. Employees feel confident in meeting deadlines and are completing more tasks. Employees report feeling accountable for their productivity and setting clear goals, indicating a higher sense of responsibility. This aligns with greater control over schedules and tasks, leading to self-direction and goal-driven behaviour. Improvements in time management, work structuring, and the ability to utilize technology effectively suggest that the nature of the work itself is perceived as more satisfying under WFH. Employees feel more effective and in control of their tasks and time. The development of new skills while working from home points to the potential for personal growth. Remote employees are more likely to engage in proactive learning and skill development, enhancing their output. Employees reported feeling more fulfilled with their personal lives, more satisfied with their work-life balance, and more in control of their lives due to WFH. These feelings align with Herzberg's motivators, like recognition and personal growth. The flexibility of the WFH arrangement enables employees to manage their work and personal responsibilities effectively, maintain a healthier balance, and have more control over their daily schedules. This relates to autonomy and responsibility, which are strong motivators in Herzberg's theory.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that the respondents have a high level of work-life balance under the Work from Home arrangement. The dimensions with the highest levels were personal satisfaction and flexibility, both described as very high, while stress level, time management, and technology and resources were rated as high. The study's findings largely **agree** with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory regarding the effect of work-from-home arrangements on the level of work-life balance and the extent of employee productivity among COA ROXII personnel. Working from home notably boosts Herzberg's motivator factors, such as achievement, responsibility, and flexibility, thereby enhancing job satisfaction, personal fulfillment, and overall work-life balance, which contributes positively to productivity. Concurrently, WFH effectively addresses key hygiene factors like stress reduction and resource availability, preventing dissatisfaction and further improving both work-life balance and productivity.

Recommendations

It is suggested that employees may actively seek and implement strategies for effective time management, as the study shows this is a key benefit of WFH, leading to more time for personal life and efficient task completion. Continue to set clear productivity goals for yourselves to maintain high levels of output and accountability in a WFH setting. Maximize the use of available technology and resources to enhance efficiency and maintain a healthy work-life balance, as access to these tools significantly contributes to productivity and satisfaction. Be intentional about setting clear boundaries between work and personal time to prevent burnout and ensure a healthy work-life balance. Utilize the flexibility offered by WFH to manage personal responsibilities and engage in hobbies, as this significantly contributes to personal satisfaction and overall well-being.

Given the high positive impact on both productivity and work-life balance, management may continue to support and potentially expand WFH options for eligible employees. Continuously assess and provide employees with the necessary technology, tools, and reliable digital infrastructure to ensure efficient task completion and work-life harmony in a WFH setup. Encourage personal accountability and goal orientation by entrusting employees with control over their schedules and tasks, which the study shows leads to increased productivity. Implement and promote programs or guidelines that help employees manage stress levels, improve time management, and maintain healthy work-life boundaries within the WFH framework. Acknowledge and reinforce the increased output, improved task completion rates, and efficient task completion demonstrated by WFH employees to further boost motivation and satisfaction.

Considering the beneficial impact of work-life balance on employee productivity, it is recommended that flexible work arrangements may be continued or strengthened. Organizations may support policies that empower employees to manage their personal and professional obligations effectively without negatively affecting their productivity. Organizations currently without WFH arrangements may consider implementing them, given the significant positive impact on employee productivity and work-life balance demonstrated in this study. Prioritize investment in robust digital tools, technology, and support systems to enable effective remote work and ensure employees have the resources needed to perform efficiently. Establish clear guidelines and expectations for WFH to ensure consistency, support employees in managing their time, maintain productivity, and recognize that WFH can contribute to reduced stress and improved personal satisfaction, making it a valuable strategy for enhancing overall employee well-being.

Future Research may build upon this study by incorporating other relevant factors such as individual motivation, the nature of the work itself, leadership approaches, access to necessary tools, or the home working environment. Investigating these additional variables may provide a more thorough understanding of the elements that shape productivity and work-life balance in work-from-home scenarios. Investigate other factors that may influence the remaining 29.3% of the variance in employee productivity under WFH, such as personal motivation, specific types of work, leadership styles, and

individual home environments. Conduct longitudinal studies to observe the long-term effects of WFH on employee productivity, work-life balance, and career progression. Supplement quantitative data with qualitative research (e.g., in-depth interviews, focus groups) to gain a deeper understanding of employees' subjective experiences and perceptions of WFH's impact. Conduct similar studies in different industries and sectors to determine if the findings are consistent across various organizational contexts and research the effects of hybrid work models (a combination of WFH and office work) on productivity and work-life balance, as this is becoming increasingly prevalent.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In adherence to the ethical guidelines stipulated by the Mindanao State University Ethics Review Committee, the researcher made sure that the values of respect, justice, and beneficence guided every step of the study. This included securing voluntary participation, protecting participants' privacy and confidentiality, thoroughly explaining the informed consent process, carefully identifying any possible risks, and considering any potential benefits for those involved that the study contains no substantial plagiarism and no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study.

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REFERENCES

- Almeida, D., & Santos, J. (2024). Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory: Relevance Today. *The Business & Management Review*, 14(1), 1-10.
- Anakpo, G., Nqwayibana, Z., & Mishi, S. (2023). The Impact of Work-from-Home on Employee Performance and Productivity: A Systematic Review. *Sustainability*, 15(5), 4529. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15054529>
- Baker, E., Avery, G. C., & Crawford, J. (2007). Satisfaction and perceived productivity when professionals work from home. *Research and practice in human resource management*, 15(1), 37-62.
- Bloom, N., Liang, J., Roberts, J. & Ying, Z. J. (2015). Does working from home work? Evidence from a Chinese experiment. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 130(1), 165–218. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qju032>
- Bryman, A. (2012). *Social Research Methods*. Oxford University Press. <https://ktpu.kpi.ua/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/social-research-methods-alan-bryman.pdf>.
- Bulger, C. A., Matthews, R. A., & Hoffman, M. E. (2021). Work and personal life boundary management: Boundary strength, work/personal life balance, and the segmentation-integration continuum. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 12(4), 365–375.
- Choudhury, P., Foroughi, C., & Larson, B. (2021). Work-from-anywhere: The productivity effects of geographic flexibility. *Strategic Management Journal*, 42(4), 655-683
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research methods in education* (8th ed.). Routledge.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2017). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Etikan, I., Musa, S. A., & Alkassim, R. S. (2016). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*, 5(1), 1-4.
- Faulds, D. J., Carter, L. L., & Payne, D. (2021). The remote work experience: Work-life conflict, isolation, and productivity.
- Fazal, S., Masood, S., Nazir, F., & Majoka, M. I. (2022). Individual and Organizational Strategies for Promoting Work-Life Balance for Sustainable Workforce: A Systematic Literature Review from Pakistan. *Sustainability*, 14(18), 11552. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141811552>
- Field, A. (2013). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics* (4th ed.). SAGE.
- Freedman, M (2024). *Management theory of Frederick Herzberg*. Business.com. <https://www.business.com/articles/management-theory-of-frederick-herzberg/>
- Gaduaena, A., Caboverde, C. E., & Flaminiano, J. P. (2022). Telework potential in the Philippines. *The Economic and Labour Relations Review*, 33(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/10353046221075103>
- Golden, T. D., & Veiga, J. F. (2005). The impact of telecommuting on role stress and work-life balance. *Journal of Management*, 31(2), 301–318. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206304271768>

- Hammer, L. B., Kossek, E. E., Anger, W. K., Bodner, T., & Zimmerman, K. L. (2010). Clarifying Work-Family Intervention Processes: The Roles of Work-Family Conflict and Family-Supportive Supervisory Behaviors. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 96(1), 134–150
- Irfan, M., Khalid, R. A., Kaka Khel, S. S. U. H., Maqsoom, A., & Sherani, I. K. (2021). Impact of work–life balance with the role of organizational support and job burnout on project performance. *Engineering Construction & Architectural Management*.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/355184576_Impact_of_work-life_balance_with_the_role_of_organizational_support_and_job_burnout_on_project_performance
- Ismawati, I., Soetjipto, B. E., & Sopiah, S. (2023). THE INFLUENCE OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND WORK FROM HOME ON WORK PRODUCTIVITY: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW (SLR). *International Journal of Business, Law, and Education*, 4(2), 587 - 599. <https://doi.org/10.56442/ijble.v4i2.212>
- Kossek, E. E., & Lautsch, B. A. (2018). Work-life flexibility for whom? Occupational status and work-life inequality in upper, middle, and lower level jobs. *The Academy of Management Annals*, 12(1), 5–36. <https://doi.org/10.5465/annals.2016.0059>
- Lomakin, V. (2022). HOW REMOTE WORK AFFECTS EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION (Publication No. 29191060) [Master's thesis, Rochester Institute of Technology]. ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global.
- Matli, W., & Wamba, S. F. (2023). Work from anywhere: inequalities in technology infrastructure distribution for digit workers. *Digital Transformation and Society*, 2(2), 149–162.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/DTS-08-2022-0042>
- McLeod, S. (2023). Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (Motivators & Hygiene Factors). *Simply Psychology*. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/herzbergs-two-factor-theory.html>
- Miller, E. D. (2020). Loneliness in the Era of COVID-19. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, Article 2219. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.02219>
- Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 42(5), 533–544.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2016). *Research methods for business students* (7th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Sim, J., & Wright, C. (2000). *Research in Health Care: Concepts, Designs and Methods*. Cheltenham: Stanley Thornes Publishers Ltd.
- Stroom, M. (2023). Measuring Work-from-Home Productivity and Stress: Restructuring, Validation, and Retest-Reliability of the Health Work Questionnaire (HWQ) and single-item scale alternatives in the Working-from-Home Context. Available from SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4360166> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4360166>